

Extraction studies of Fe^{III} metal ion from hydrobromic acid medium using Cyanex-923 extractant

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Abstract : A systematic study of solvent extraction of Fe^{III} from hydrobromic acid medium using neutral phosphine oxide extractant, Cyanex-923 in toluene has been proposed. This metal ion was found to be quantitatively extracted with Cyanex-923 in toluene in the acidic range of 6–7 M HBr and from the organic phase it is stripped back into the aqueous phase with water. The effect of HBr concentration, reagent concentration, equilibrium period, effect of diluents, effect of equilibration period and stripping agent on the extraction of Fe^{III} has been studied. The stoichiometry of the extracted species was determined on the basis of slope analysis method. Based on these results a sequential procedure for their separation from each other was developed.

Keywords : Extraction, iron, HBr, Cyanex-923, stripping, separation.

Introduction

Dibenzo-18-crown-6 has been used for the extraction and separation of Fe^{III} from other cations in hydrobromic acid medium¹. Separations of iron and zinc from manganese nodule leach liquor were carried out from HCl solution using tributyl phosphate and methyl iso-butyl ketone dissolved in kerosene². Determination of Cr^{III}, Fe^{III}, Ni^{II}, Pb^{II} and Zn^{II} ions in environmental sample were studied by solvent extraction using a triketone reagent³. Extraction of Fe^{III} was also carried from the chloride leach liquor using Aliquat-336⁴. Separation studies of various metals ions like Cu^{II}, Fe^{III}, Zn^{II} and Ni^{II} was done from nitrate solution using LK-C2⁵. Solvent extraction of Fe^{III} from Zn^{II} solutions by octylphenyl acid phosphate and di-(2-ethylhexyl) phosphoric acid were studied⁶. Recently Cyanex-reagents like Cyanex-302 and Cyanex-301 have been used for the extraction of Fe^{III} from chloride, nitrate or sulphate media^{7–9}. A solvent extraction method for the separation of Fe^{III} from Co^{II} in nitric acid medium has been developed by using Cyanex-923 in *n*-dodecane¹⁰. The extraction of Mg^{II}, Al^{III}, Ti^{IV}, V^V, Cr^{III}, Mn^{II} and Fe^{III} from HCl solution has been investigated by using Cyanex-923 in kerosene¹¹. Separation of Fe^{III} from strong ZnSO₄-H₂SO₄ solution was investigated by

comparing the performance of octylphenyl acid phosphate and di-(2-ethylhexyl) phosphoric acid at different temperatures¹². The use of *N,N*-dimethyl-*N,N'*-diphenyl malonamide and *N,N'*-dimethyl-*N,N'*-diphenyl tetradecyl malonamide for the extraction of Fe^{III} from HCl solution was investigated¹³. Solvent extraction of Fe^{III} from nitrate media using bis(2-ethylhexyl) phosphinic acid extractant were also carried out¹⁴. A solvent extraction process using Primene JMT as the extractant was investigated to remove Fe^{III} from an Al₂(SO₄)₃ solution¹⁵.

The present paper deals with extraction of Fe^{III} from hydrobromic acid medium using Cyanex-923 extractant diluted in toluene.

Method and materials :

Apparatus and reagents :

Cyanex-923 extractant supplied by Cytec Industries Inc. Canada, were used without further purification. A known amount of ferric ammonium sulphate, was dissolved in minimum quantity of sulphuric acid and diluted with double distilled water as per requirement. All other chemicals used were of analytical grade. Elico model LI 120 pH meter with combined glass electrode was used for H⁺ ions concentration studies and Shimadzu UV-

Visible Recording spectrophotometer model UV-2401PC with 10 mm cortex quartz cuvettes for absorbance measurements.

Procedure :

A solution containing 50 μg of Fe^{III} and 6.0 M HBr is taken in 10 ml and was equilibrated with equal volume of Cyanex-923 in toluene for the required shaking time of 10 min. The two phases were allowed to separate and the organic phase containing the metal extracted species was then stripped quantitatively with water. The amount of Fe^{III} was then determined spectrophotometrically at 480 nm with thiocyanate method¹⁶. All the experiments were carried out at room temperature.

Results and discussion

Effect of hydrobromic acid concentration on the percentage extraction of Fe^{III} :

The extraction of Fe^{III} metal ion was studied at various HBr concentrations ranging from 1.0–7.0 M . As the HBr concentration increases the extraction goes on increasing and becomes quantitative in the range 6.0–7.0 M with Cyanex-923 diluted in toluene. Therefore all the extraction studies were carried out at 6.0 M HBr.

Effect of reagent concentration on percentage extraction of Fe^{III} :

Quantitative extraction of Fe^{III} was observed at 6.0 M HBr. Hence keeping the acidity fixed, the extraction of Fe^{III} was then carried out by varying the concentration of Cyanex-923 reagent (5×10^{-4} – 1×10^{-1} M). During the extraction the other parameter like period of extraction, diluent and temperature were kept constant. It was observed that as the concentration of reagent increases the extraction also increases and it becomes quantitative in the range 5×10^{-3} – 1×10^{-1} M cyanex-923. The minimum concentration of Cyanex-923 required for the quantitative extraction of Fe^{III} was found to be 5×10^{-3} M in toluene.

Effect of various diluents and period of equilibration :

The extraction of Fe^{III} with Cyanex-923 was carried using different aliphatic and aromatic diluents like carbon tetrachloride, chloroform, *n*-hexane, toluene, xylene and cyclohexane. Quantitative extraction was observed with all the above diluents except that of *n*-hexane (91.5%) and cyclohexane (85.8%). Toluene was used as diluent for the extraction of Fe^{III} in HBr. Extraction equilibrium was

studied for different periods of shaking ranging from 1–30 min. It was observed that 3 min of shaking period was sufficient for quantitative extraction of Fe^{III} with 0.005 M Cyanex-923 in toluene. However there was no adverse effect by increasing the extraction period upto 30 min.

Effect of stripping agents :

The Fe^{III} which was extracted in the organic phase of Cyanex-923 was stripped with different strengths of acids like HCl, HNO_3 and H_2SO_4 . The complete recovery of Fe^{III} from metal loaded organic phase of Cyanex-923 was found with water and 1.0–2.0 M H_2SO_4 . The other acids showed incomplete recovery of Fe^{III} (Table 1).

Table 1. Effect of stripping agents on percentage recovery of Fe^{III} from metal loaded organic phase of Cyanex-923 in toluene

Acids	Percentage recovery (%R) of Fe^{III} from organic phase of Cyanex-923		
	HCl	HNO_3	H_2SO_4
Molarity			
1.0	72.8	76.7	99.9
2.0	92.1	75.0	99.9
3.0	65.4	70.4	–
4.0	57.4	60.3	–
Water			99.9

Stoichiometry of the extracted species :

In order to ascertain the composition of extracted species, a graph of $\log D$ versus $\log R$ was plotted. The slopes obtained were 1.93 indicating that two molecules of Cyanex-923 react with one molecule of Fe^{III} ion. Therefore the stoichiometry of the extracted species is 1 : 2. As Cyanex-923 is neutral extractant it will extract neutral species from the aqueous phase. Since extraction of Fe^{III} is carried out in hydrobromic acid media, the possible extractable species is HFeBr_4 . Therefore the probable nature of the extracted species in the organic phase was found to be $\text{HFeBr}_4 \cdot 2\text{Cyanex-923}$.

Influence of temperature :

To determine the influence of temperature on extraction of Fe^{III} , an experiment of extraction is carried out at 3.0 M HBr with 0.005 M Cyanex-923 in toluene at different temperatures ranging upto 70.0 $^\circ\text{C}$. The distribution ratio decreased with increase in temperature. As per the Van't Hoff equation of $\log D_{\text{Fe}} = (-\Delta H/2.303 RT) + C$, where D_{Fe} represent the distribution ratio, ΔH is the enthalpy change for the reaction and C is the constant. The

Table 2. Separation of Fe^{III} from multicomponent mixtures with Cyanex-923 in toluene

Sr. No.	Metal ions	Amount taken (µg)	Conc. HBr	Extractant Cyanex-923	Stripping agents	Percentage recovery (%)
1.	Fe ^{III}	50	6.0 M	5 × 10 ⁻³ M	Water	99.8
	Cu ^{II}	20	-	-	Unextracted	99.2
2.	Fe ^{III}	50	6.0 M	5 × 10 ⁻³ M	Water	99.9
	Ti ^{IV}	20	-	-	Unextracted	99.3
3.	Fe ^{III}	50	6.0 M	5 × 10 ⁻³ M	Water	99.8
	Be ^{II}	15	-	-	0.5 M NaOH	99.2
4.	Fe ^{III}	50	6.0 M	5 × 10 ⁻³ M	Water	99.8
	Zn ^{II}	20	-	-	1.0 M HCl	99.5
5.	Fe ^{III}	50	6.0 M	5 × 10 ⁻³ M	Water	99.9
	Pd ^{II}	50	-	-	1 : 1 HCl+HClO ₄	98.9
6.	Fe ^{III}	50	6.0 M	5 × 10 ⁻³ M	Water	99.7
	Pt ^{IV}	50	-	-	6.0 M HClO ₄	98.7
7.	Fe ^{III}	50	6.0 M	5 × 10 ⁻³ M	Water	99.9
	Hg ^{II}	50	-	-	Unextracted	98.9

plot of $\log D_{Fe}$ versus $1/T \times 1000$ was drawn and the slope obtained was 2.092 which is used for the calculation of change in enthalpy (ΔH) of the system. The ΔH value calculated was found to be -40.06 kJ/mol, indicating the extraction reaction is exothermic in nature.

Separation of Fe^{III} from other metal ions :

Fe^{III} was separated from various other metal ions, by exploiting the differences in their respective extracting and stripping conditions (Table 2). A solution containing Fe^{III} and Cu^{II} is extracted with 5 × 10⁻³ M Cyanex-923 in toluene at 6.0 M HBr, when Fe^{III} gets only extracted in the organic phase while Cu^{II} remained unextracted in the aqueous phase. The extracted Fe^{III} was then stripped with water. Similarly Fe^{III} is separated from the other metal ions like Ti^{IV}, Be^{II}, Zn^{II}, Pd^{II}, Pt^{IV} and Hg^{II}.

Conclusion

- (1) The results obtained showed that extraction of Fe^{III} is possible with Cyanex-923 diluted in toluene in the hydrobromic acid range of 6.0–7.0.
- (2) The ΔH value calculated from the study of effect of temperature on extraction of Fe^{III} was found to be -40.06 kJ mol⁻¹ which clearly shows that the extraction of Fe^{III} with Cyanex-923 is exothermic in nature.
- (3) The stoichiometry of the extracted species was found to be 1 : 2. Fe^{III} was extracted into the

organic phase by solvation reaction as HFeBr₄·2Cyanex-923.

- (4) Di-*n*-butylthio phosphoric acid¹⁷ and di-(2-ethylhexyl) phosphoric acid¹⁸ extracts Fe^{III} only 90% and 50% respectively. But quantitative extraction of Fe^{III} was observed with Cyanex-923 in toluene.
- (5) The reagent concentration required for the quantitative extraction of Fe^{III} with Di-*o*-tolyl phosphoric acid¹⁹ was 0.3 M in benzene and with di-(2-ethylhexyl) phosphoric acid¹⁸ was 0.4 M in isodecanol. However with present extractant, it requires only 0.005 M Cyanex-923 in toluene.

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